

Study of Limited Face-to-Face Learning Policy Indonesia

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Abstract: The coronavirus pandemic that has occurred throughout the world has been running for more than a year and Indonesia has experienced it since March 2020. This makes learning done using "online" (using the internet network). At the start of the new academic year 2021-2022, the Government of Indonesia in terms of the Ministry of Education and Culture allowed the Limited Face-to-face Learning model for some schools which were considered to be at a certain level that would not be dangerous if the policy was implemented. The problems in this study are as follows: Is the implementation of Limited Face-to-Face Learning still an obstacle at the Aufa Saif Natural School; the extent to which the limited face-to-face learning rules are complied with at the school where the study is located; Are the facilities and infrastructure related to the implementation of Limited Face-to-face Learning completed by the target school; The purpose of the study was to describe the concept of applying Limited Face-to-face Learning at the Aufa Saif Natural School – South Tangerang. The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach with data validity techniques using triangulation techniques.

Keywords: *Face to face learning, policy, Aufa saif School*

I. Introduction

The coronavirus pandemic that has occurred throughout the world has been running for more than a year and Indonesia has experienced it since March 2020. This makes learning done using "online" (using the internet network). At the start of the new academic year 2021, the Government of Indonesia in terms of the Ministry of Education and Culture allowed the Limited Face-to-face Learning model for some schools which were considered to be at a certain level that would not be dangerous if the policy was implemented.

The correct concept of Limited Face-to-Face Learning is to regulate the number of students in each class to be less than the normal number and the amount of study time allocation is also reduced. This limited face-to-face learning definition provides two options for students, namely face-to-face learning and distance learning. This face-to-face learning will take effect in the new academic year 2021/2022. Meanwhile,

districts/cities that are still in the red zone carry out distance learning (PJJ) or online learning.

Director of Elementary Schools, Ministry of education and culture, research and technology in Indonesia, Dra. Sri Wahyuningsih, M.Pd said (<https://ditpsd.kemdikbud.go.id/article/>) that during the pandemic it resulted in learning achievement gaps, namely: (1) academic achievement decreased; (2) cyberbullying (cyberbullying); (3) increased risk of early marriage; (4) exploitation of children, especially girls and teenage pregnancy.

The data shows that face-to-face learning has been implemented throughout Indonesia, namely PAUD (8,989); SD (25,260); SMP (8,233); and high school (2,940). This data shows that the Ministry of Education and Culture has made efforts to (1) maintain the quality of learning for Indonesian children; (2) keep the mentality of Indonesian children to return to offline learning; (3) Indonesian children can access the same learning materials without any problems; (4) students can more quickly understand the material presented; (5) The burden on parents is reduced due to the use of a large quota; (6) minimize the occurrence of lost of learning and psychosocial risks to children; (7) the interaction between teachers/lecturers and students can take place maximally; (8) Teachers/lecturers can interact optimally with students/students. (9) Teachers/lecturers can supervise in following the material and completing assignments.

Implementation of limited face-to-face learning or in accordance with the arrangements in the Joint Decree of four ministers, namely the Minister of Education and Culture, the Minister of Religion, the Minister of Health, and the Minister of Home Affairs number 03/KB/2021, number 384 of 2021, number HK 01.08/MENKES /4242/2021, Number 440-717 of 2021 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Learning during the 2019 Coronavirus Disease Pandemic (Covid-19).

There are five provisions that must be complied with in implementing Limited Face-to-face Learning in accordance with the Decrees of the four Ministers, namely: (1) Must pay attention to maintaining a minimum distance of 1.5 meters and a maximum of 18 students per class (about 50%); (2) The number of days and hours of face-to-face learning is limited by using the division of study groups (shifts) in accordance with the provisions of each educational unit; (3) Always use a three-layer cloth mask, wash hands with soap, apply cough/sneeze etiquette; (4) Students must be in good health; (5) Activities that have the potential to become a crowd are not allowed to occur in the education unit.

Aufa Saif Natural School located at Jalan Jati no.61 RT 012/08 Melati Mas, Pondok Jagung, South Tangerang. Mini-style schools are schools that have implemented Limited Face-to-face Learning in the new academic year 2021-2022. The Aufa Saif Natural School was used as the object of research because it was different from other conventional schools. This school is the object of research because it is different from conventional schools. This school consists of a playgroup, Kindergarten and Elementary School. Aufa Saif

Nature School has a conceptual approach to nature so that students can play freely with a large yard and garden equipped with various games, for an example tree house, mini outbound, and other natural games.

This school has implemented Limited Face-to-face Learning and followed all the protocols set by the Ministry of Education and Culture, including (1) every student entering school must wash their hands which have been provided by the school in the front yard (soap and water); (2) not shaking hands with the teacher who greeted him in front of the class; (3) carry hand sanitizer in their respective bags; (4) study only 3 hours a day; (5) Study not every day, only three days a week.

Teaching and learning activities are fun because learning activities always vary, for example PAUD children do sports activities, rocking, color, learn to shop at the supermarket, plant flowers, play with the Sakinah family using dolls, and plantation medicinal trees (lemongrass, turmeric). ginger, galangal, and others), as well as many other activities.

Formulation of the problem:

Based on the background of the problems described above, the formulation of the problem in this study is How to Implement Limited Face-to-face Learning at the Aufa Saif Natural School

II. Method

2.1 Research approach and methodology

The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. According to Sugiyono, 2005 qualitative research is not too focused on numbers or values in measuring variables. While quantitative research is research that departs from data, utilizes existing theories as explanatory material and ends with a theory. The purpose of qualitative research is to explain the phenomenon as deeply as possible by collecting the deepest data, which shows the importance of depth and detail of the data being studied.

Some points of qualitative research are:

1. Qualitative research is not too focused on numbers or values in measuring the variables.
2. Qualitative research does not conduct a test using statistical methods
3. It is elaborative, researchers are allowed to dig deeper into the object of research without relying on numerical measurements
4. More structured than quantitative research

2.1.1 The definition of qualitative research according to several experts:

The definition of qualitative research according to several experts:

1. According to Sugiyono: This method is used to examine the condition of natural objects, where the researcher is the key instrument

2. According to Saryono: Research used to investigate social influences that cannot be explained and measured through a quantitative approach
3. According to Strauss and Corbin: Research that produces findings that cannot be obtained by statistical procedures

According to Creswell (2012), qualitative research is divided into five types, namely:

1. Phenomenological Research: researchers collect data by observation to find out the participants' essential phenomena in their life experiences
2. Grounded Theory: Researchers can draw generalized conclusions (what is observed inductively)
3. Ethnography: Researchers carry out group culture according to its natural conditions
4. Case Studies: Researchers conduct in-depth exploration of programs, events, and processes against one or more persons.
5. Narrative Research: Researchers obtain data about the life journey of a person or more and compiled it into narrative and chronological reports.

2.1.2 Data and data resources

Data is very essential to explain a situation or problem, and data is also treated to answer the research focus.

This study uses data obtained from two sources, namely:

1) Primary data

Primary data is data obtained from the source directly, observed, and recorded directly, such as interviews, observations, and questionnaires, with related parties, such as school coconuts, class teachers, and others.

2) Secondary Data is data obtained from existing data and has a problem relationship that is examined.

This data is obtained from several supporting sources, from books, the internet, journals, and so on (this data is useful to complete primary data).

2.1.3 Data Collection Techniques and Instruments

1) Observation (Observation)

According to Sugiyono (2014:145) "observation is a complex process, a process composed of various biological and psychological processes". According to Riyanto (2010: 96) "observation is a data collection method that uses direct or indirect observations.

2) Interview (Interview)

Interviews were conducted in this study in order to obtain adequate data or strengthen the data that has been obtained from the results of observations. According to Esterberg in Sugiyono (2015: 72) interviews are meetings held to exchange information and ideas by way of question and answer, so that it can be reduced to a conclusion or meaning in a particular topic.

3) Questioner

a technique of collecting data from a number of people or respondents through a set of questions to be answered. By providing the list of questions, the answers obtained are then collected as data. The process of collecting data using a closed questionnaire can make it easier for researchers because the questionnaire has provided answer choices. So that the answers from respondents are more focused and also do not deviate from the expected answers. Questionnaires were given to parents and teachers

III. Result

- a) The results of interviews with parents and teachers consist of three indicators, namely (1) distance learning; (2) distance learning styles and strategies; (3) Limited face-to-face learning styles and strategies.

All respondents (8 parents and 2 teachers) answer for the indicator first, distance learning: They Can you use all applications installed on your computer or mobile phone. They Can install the application by themselves. They don't have any problems with software or application, but if they have a problem able to solve it by themself. They use google, chrome, browser, youtube, and Facebook. They can be using the internet at home smoothly. They always use applications Intagram, Facebook, Shoppee and Toko Pedia, and others. Schools always using google meet and zoom meeting.

Indicator second, distance learning styles and strategies: They prepare children using laptops or Handphones. They argue that online learning is very boring and students cannot concentrate during the length of learning. They also argue that online learning is not good, only compulsion with the pandemic conditions. They answered that the benchmarks/references used by parents/teachers to know that students understand the material presented online are: they can answer questions asked by the teacher ang parents. They answered that there was a time limit for submitting assignments given by the teacher, even though online. They answered that the biggest challenge of learning online is that children are not focused on learning and it is rather difficult to inculcate the subject matter.

Indicator third, Limited face-to-face learning styles and strategies: parents answered that the preparations made during face-to-face meetings were limited, including: stationery, food supplies, and other

supporting tools. They say that face-to-face learning is more fun and enjoyable and easy to follow the subject matter. They say that their children can easily follow face-to-face learning. They also said that face-to-face learning made it easier for their children to repeat lessons at home and tell stories about what the teacher taught at school. They say that with face-to-face learning there is a time limit for collecting assignments given by the teacher. They said that with face-to-face learning they did not experience any obstacles or difficulties and their children were very happy to learn face-to-face

- b) The results of the answers to the questionnaire which were filled out by 2 teachers related to face-to-face learning consisted of 4 indicators, namely: (1) Teacher's understanding of face-to-face learning; (2) teachers' understanding of authentic assessment; (3) teachers' understanding of integrated thematic learning in kindergartens; and (4) teachers' understanding of scientific learning in kindergarten.

All respondents answer for the indicator first, the Teacher's understanding of face-to-face learning. The teacher always talks by involving several studies to provide meaningful knowledge to students. The teacher always describes objects or events which contain a number of concepts/materials from various subjects. Teachers always match concepts holistically. Teachers always map the merging of various fields of study. The teacher often demonstrates material related to the knowledge that students have previously. The teacher always demonstrates all the fields of study that he masters. The teacher always formulates material from various subjects that are combined in-depth. The teacher always concludes the development of the planned topic.

Indicator second is teachers' understanding of authentic assessment. The teacher always emphasizes the assessment of students' abilities according to what students do in the learning process. The teacher always explains the assessment which must reflect the students' real problems every day. The teacher always matches the assessment of the process and the results at once with what is. The teacher always maps the assessment covering the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. The teacher always demonstrates according to the characteristics of the type of subject. The teacher always demonstrates the understanding that students have gained in learning. The teacher always summarizes the assessment of learning achievement. The teacher always concludes the assessment criteria that are clearer for students.

Indicator Third, teachers' understanding of integrated thematic learning in kindergartens. The teacher always explains certain themes in the learning process. The teacher always explains the discussion of the theme in terms of various subjects. The teacher always matches other concepts that he understands. The teacher always makes an analogy with the students' interests and preferences. The teacher always

demonstrates learning in accordance with the problems that students often encounter in their environment. The teacher always demonstrates the process and material that is not fragmented. The teacher always summarizes the concepts of the various subjects studied to be interrelated. The teacher is always together with the students to share perspectives on a theme.

Indicator Fourth, is teachers' understanding of scientific learning in kindergarten. The teacher always describes the understanding of the material using a scientific approach. The teacher always explains every step of scientific learning. Teachers always map scientific and non-scientific learning. Teachers always make analogies with phenomena that have similarities and differences. Teachers always exemplify the scientific process of constructing concepts. Teachers always describe ways to use tools and materials in scientific learning. Teachers and students always conclude from data or information processing activities. The teacher always summarizes various concepts that have been constructed by students.

- c) The results of learning observations in classroom assessments are: Students 1. Preparing materials; 2. Pray together; 3. Listening to teacher checking; 4. Provide answers to teacher questions in apperception activities; 5. Listening to the teacher's explanation of the lesson plan/objectives (grouping, discussion, use of learning media, teaching aids, etc.); 6. Asking questions to the teacher in apperception activities;

Carry out plant observation activities: a) Listening to the teacher's explanation; b) Teacher demonstration; c) Student demonstration; d) Viewing images/video views; e) Read books/other sources.

Students do the following activities: Discuss, Ask, Questioning, Give reasons, Expressing ideas. The teacher and students conclude the concepts/themes they have learned (as well as reinforcement) Reflection: • What has/not been mastered/understood; Their feelings while studying; The way they learn is related to success/failure in mastering an ability/understanding; The relationship of spiritual and social attitudes with the material that has been studied.

Take notes on assignments given by the teacher and listening to the teacher's explanation of the material/topic/theme/sub-theme that will be studied in the next meeting.

Research Thinking Framework

IV. Discussion

Based on the research findings above, there are two conclusions, namely online learning and face-to-face learning.

a) Online Learning

The advantages of implementing e-learning:

1. Easily accessible: Simply using a smartphone or other technological device such as a laptop connected to the internet, you can access the material you want to learn. By implementing e-learning you can carry out learning activities anywhere, anytime.
2. More affordable cost: Of course, we all want to increase knowledge without financial constraints. With an internet data package, you can access a variety of learning materials without worrying about missing a lesson if you don't attend. It is recommended that you register as a member in e-learning

because member fees are cheaper than taking lessons or courses at learning institutions.

3. Flexible study time: Usually most people who want to learn more do not have enough time. One of the reasons may be because your time is already used for work. Digital-based learning or e-learning is the solution. Time to study can be done at any time without being tied to study hours.

4. Broad insight: By implementing e-learning, of course you will find many things that you did not know before. This is because some of the subject matter available in e-learning is not yet available in print media such as books which are often used in conventional teaching and learning methods. This is different from face-to-face learning which is done by reading books.

Disadvantages of implementing e-learning:

1. Limited internet access: One of the shortcomings of the e-learning learning method is the limited internet access. If you are in an area that does not have stable internet coverage, it will be difficult for you to access e-learning services. Of course, this still happens a lot in Indonesia, considering that some 3T areas (lagging, frontier, and outermost) are still not covered by internet access. In addition, the price of internet data usage is still considered quite expensive for some Indonesian people. This causes the ability to take advantage of e-learning is still considered a privilege.
2. Less interaction with teachers: Some e-learning learning methods are one-way. This causes the interaction of teachers and students to be reduced so it will be difficult for you to get further explanations about material that is difficult to understand.
3. Understanding of the material: The material taught in e-learning is responded to based on different levels of understanding, depending on the ability of the user. Some people may be able to grasp material faster just by reading, but there are also those who take longer to really understand. There are even those who need explanations from other people in order to understand the material being studied.
4. Lack of Supervision in Learning: Lack of supervision in conducting online learning makes e-learning users sometimes lose focus. With the ease of access, some users tend to procrastinate studying. Self-awareness is needed so that the online learning process becomes directed and achieves goals. Stay healthy and always keep our spirit up!

- b) Face to face learning

The Advantages face to face Learning

1. **Monitored Students:** Students are monitored. Although traditional, face-to-face learning or offline learning certainly makes all student activities and various competencies clearly monitored by the teacher. Teachers will find it easier to monitor student activities, both academically and non-academically to encourage their development.
2. **More Focused Students:** Students are more focused. Besides being more monitored, this learning also makes students more focused on learning. Directly, students can learn and do assignments without internet network interference or tools so that they can learn smoothly. In addition, students can also focus more on learning and are not distracted by distractions that might break their learning focus.
3. **Clear Standardization:** Standardization is clear. Not only learning materials and curriculum can be delivered clearly, the teachers and the material are also clearly certified. So that teachers can deliver material with their abilities and knowledge as the capacity of educators, and the material delivered is also in accordance with standards.
4. **Students Noticed:** Students are noticed. Students who do not understand the material can directly ask questions without being limited by space and time. So that offline learning allows students to more easily understand and receive learning materials.

Disadvantages face to face learning:

- 1) **Distance in Learning:** Distance in learning. Offline learning activities have the disadvantage that it requires a physical classroom. So that students and teachers must meet, face to face in the same place and time, and must interact directly. That is, it takes time to cover the distance to gain knowledge, ethics, and psychology.
- 2) **Study Time:** Study time. In addition to distance, time to study offline also requires uniformity. Students must gather in the same place and according to the time specified, so that high discipline is needed in order to be present on time. If you relax for too long, of course this becomes a problem for students to adjust.
- 3) **Lack of Independence:** Lack of independence. Offline or traditional learning classes are still lacking when compared to online learning. This is because students must be led to learn and sometimes teachers have to be forced to focus on learning. Therefore, students lack the awareness to learn and gain knowledge.
- 4) **At risk of contracting Covid-19:** At risk of contracting Covid-19. Although such prevention has been carried out, offline learning cannot rule out the possibility of being more susceptible to being exposed to or contracting the corona virus, so that it is not optimal if it is carried out in the current Covid-19 pandemic

situation.

- 5) Limited Knowledge of Technology: Limited knowledge of technology. If it is carried out continuously, then teachers and students feel facilitated by the ease of direct learning so that they cannot or are unable to explore their abilities to use technology and information such as laptops, PCs, use of applications on the internet, and so on.
- 6) Infrastructure: Infrastructure. When offline learning has to be carried out in the era of the Covid-19 pandemic, larger or adequate infrastructure facilities are needed to create health protocols, so the costs incurred for hand washing, hand sanitizer, masks, face shields, and even temperature gauges must be spent.

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